

Experimental Comparison of Different Pressure Gain Measurement Techniques for RDCs

Tim Kayser*, Hongyi Wei†, Eric Bach‡, Christian Oliver Paschereit§, and Myles D. Bohon¶
Technische Universität Berlin, 10623 Berlin, Germany

Rotating Detonation Combustors (RDC) feature an inherently unsteady internal flow field with characteristic frequencies in the kHz range, which makes accurately quantifying the achieved pressure gain challenging. The present study therefore considers three methods to determine the stagnation pressure of the high-enthalpy outlet flow: Mach-corrected Capillary Tube Averaged Pressure (CTAP) measurements of $p_{t,4}$, direct Kiel probe measurements of $p_{t,8}$, and Equivalent Available Pressure (EAP) measurements using a thrust stand. The methods differ significantly in their relative accuracy and the amount of required instrumentation. A parametric study with all three approaches was conducted at TU Berlin over a range of configurations and operating conditions to compare the acquired data. To this end, a 5 kN class thrust stand was used along with a calibration method and base drag measurement setup. Further, a low Mach number correction was implemented for Mach-corrected CTAP and EAP data at conditions where the $M_8 = 1$ assumption breaks down. The EAP data displays the highest amount of scattering due to the large number of calibration that need to be taken into account. The base drag pressure distribution on the outlet flanges, which can amount to 12.78% and more of EAP, varies significantly with the operating condition. All three methods generally agree well with one another, with EAP being the most conservative. Kiel probe measured stagnation pressure is on average about 5% higher than EAP and 3% higher than the Mach-corrected $p_{t,4}$. This underlines that methods with reduced instrumentation may be useful for pressure gain estimation. Nevertheless, it also shows that a standardized data reporting method may be required in the community to compare different experiments.

Nomenclature

Symbols

A	=	area
F	=	force
J	=	mass flux
M	=	Mach number
\dot{m}	=	mass flow rate
p	=	pressure
t	=	time
γ	=	ratio of specific heats
ϕ	=	equivalence ratio

Abbreviations

CTAP	=	Capillary Tube Averaged Pressure
EAP	=	Equivalent Available Pressure
PGC	=	Pressure Gain Combustion
RDC	=	Rotating Detonation Combustion

Subscripts and Superscripts

$(\cdot)_{\text{atm}}$	=	atmospheric
$(\cdot)_{\text{bd}}$	=	base drag
$(\cdot)_{\text{g}}$	=	gross
$(\cdot)_{\text{net}}$	=	net
$(\cdot)_{\text{s}}$	=	static
$(\cdot)_{\text{t}}$	=	total
$\overline{(\cdot)}$	=	derived value

Station Numbers

0	=	ambient conditions
2	=	air plenum
3.1	=	air injector throat
3.2	=	combustion annulus
4	=	combustor exit
8	=	outlet throat

*Graduate Student, Aerospace Engineering, working at TU Berlin, enrolled at TU Braunschweig.

†PhD Student, Chair of Pressure Gain Combustion, TU Berlin.

‡Postdoctoral Researcher, Chair of Pressure Gain Combustion, TU Berlin, AIAA Student Member.

§Professor, Chair of Fluid Dynamics, TU Berlin, AIAA Associate Fellow.

¶Professor, Chair of Pressure Gain Combustion, TU Berlin, AIAA Member.

I. Introduction

In order to achieve higher efficiency in power generations and propulsion applications, Pressure Gain Combustion (PGC) has become an active field of research [1]. Unlike conventional constant pressure combustion systems, a PGC process is inherently unsteady due to an either detonative or a deflagrative combustion of reactants. The concept aims to efficiently convert the chemical energy from the fuel by increasing the stagnation pressure of the product gases relative to the reactants. In this context, one of the most promising implementations of PGC is the Rotating Detonation Combustor (RDC). The geometrically simple device consists of a continuously fed fuel/oxidizer injector system and an annular chamber where detonation waves propagate into the fresh reactant mixture. The high-enthalpy jet exiting an RDC is then either converted to mechanical work through a turbine or used for thrust generation. The technology promises a step change in efficiency in both the energy sector and the aeronautics and aerospace sector [2].

The actual measurement of pressure gain is a crucial task to assess the performance of RDCs. In principle, an RDC produces a higher total pressure exiting the combustion chamber compared to the entering reactants. However, time-accurate pressure measurements at the frequencies of operation are challenging due to the harsh environment and short time-scales of relevance inside the combustor. The unforgiving environment of the detonation zone makes accurate measurements more complicated. Defining and quantifying an appropriately averaged value is thus not trivial [3].

At present, there are three major proposed methods to quantify the flow stagnation pressure in the RDC, with the application of a Kiel probe the only direct measurement method. Bach et al. present a detailed description on the applicability of Kiel probes to RDC flow fields [4–6] and installed Kiel probes in the RDC exit plane to directly measure stagnation pressure over a wide range of operating and boundary conditions. As shown in Figure 1, the pressure gain measured by Kiel probes is in generally good agreement with the pressure gain obtained from other experiments and numerical simulations. Kiel probes present an affordable method to measure stagnation pressure while not requiring additional assumptions of the flow field, but their interaction with the outlet flow and appropriate averaging methods remain areas of active research.

Fig. 1 Comparison of various published data on RDC stagnation pressure gain over the outlet throat to oxidizer injection area ratio, reproduced from [6].

In contrast, the other two methods both require a converging section at the aft end of the RDC to define a throat where the sonic condition can be established. These are (1) the Equivalent Available Pressure (EAP) method based on thrust measurements, and (2) the Mach-corrected CTAP approach that places a pressure tap close to the exit plane of an RDC.

Kaemming and Paxson first proposed the Equivalent Available Pressure (EAP) method for total pressure measurements in RDCs [7]. It is defined as "the flow stagnation pressure which is representative of a flows ability to do work or provide thrust", and allows for a comparison of the work or thrust potential between RDCs and conventional devices. EAP replaces varying total pressure with time-averaged values. This method considers the average stagnation pressure at the combustor exit as a function of gross thrust and base drag measurements, which is then determined using the following equations:

$$F_g = p_8 A_8 (1 + \gamma M_8^2) - p_0 A_8 = F_{\text{net}} + F_{\text{bd}} \quad (1)$$

$$\tilde{p}_{s,8} = \frac{\frac{F_{\text{net}} + F_{\text{bd}}}{A_8} + p_0}{1 + \gamma M_8^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{p_{s,8}}{p_{t,8}} = \left(1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M_8^2\right)^{\frac{-\gamma}{\gamma - 1}} \quad (3)$$

with M_8 the axial Mach number at the exit throat, F_{net} the thrust measured from a load cell, and F_{bd} the base drag, i.e. the force acting on the aft surfaces due to jet expansion. The exit is assumed to be choked ($M_8 = 1$), and the average stagnation pressure at the exit plane is then calculated from Eq. 3 with $p_{s,8}$.

Fievisohn et al. found that dissipation effects such as heat losses across the combustion chamber and base drag losses at the combustor exit can prevent an actual pressure gain [8], so applying this method to measure the total pressure requires not only a robust and well-calibrated thrust stand but also an accurate quantification of the base drag at the RDC exit plane. This can require extensive instrumentation as pointed out by Harroun et al. [9].

The third approach - also referred to as the NPS method [10] - involves a capillary tube averaged pressure (CTAP) probe (see Paxson and Hoke [11]) close to the exit plane. Assuming a choked exit throat ($M_8 = 1$), the Mach number at the CTAP location can be calculated from the area-Mach number relation as

$$\frac{A}{A_8} = \left(\frac{\gamma + 1}{2}\right)^{-\frac{\gamma+1}{2(\gamma-1)}} \frac{\left(1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} M^2\right)^{\frac{\gamma+1}{2(\gamma-1)}}}{M} \quad (4)$$

where A is the channel area at the CTAP location. A simple root-finding algorithm can solve for the Mach number, which is then used to calculate a stagnation pressure from the measured static pressure as above with Eq. 3.

Brophy and Codoni [10, 12, 13] measured the total pressure derived from a CTAP static chamber pressure measurement at the combustor exit and compared the total pressures with the EAP method. Results show that the differences between the EAP value and derived CTAP total pressures were very small. However, they also point out that accurate measurements require a multitude of CTAPs and potentially also an additional pressure averaging device.

Both Mach-corrected CTAP method and EAP assume the high-enthalpy flow is choked at the exit throat. The actual Mach number varies spatially and temporally around the combustor [14], so the sonic assumption that is functional for steady flow will not be appropriate for the transient RDC system. Fievisohn et al. [15] measured the total pressure by EAP and Mach-corrected CTAP method and compared the static pressure at the exit throat based on these two methods. They found that for low mass flow rate configurations, the static pressure is lower than the atmospheric pressure due to the sonic assumption, which is non-physical for a subsonic flow. Therefore, they applied a correction of the Mach number assumption that equates pressure at the exit throat to ambient pressure ($p_8 = p_0$), and then calculated the corrected Mach number and the total pressure in an isentropic flow with the EAP method based on Eq. 5, and also by the CTAP method based on simultaneous solution of Eqns. 6 and 7.

$$\tilde{M}_8 = \sqrt{\frac{F_g}{p_8 A_8 \gamma}} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{A_4}{A_8} = \frac{\tilde{M}_8}{\tilde{M}_4} \left(\frac{\left(1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} \tilde{M}_8^2\right)^{\frac{\gamma+1}{2(\gamma-1)}}}{\left(1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} \tilde{M}_4^2\right)^{\frac{\gamma+1}{2(\gamma-1)}}} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{p_4}{p_8} = \left(\frac{\left(1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} \tilde{M}_8^2\right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}}}{\left(1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} \tilde{M}_4^2\right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}}} \right) \quad (7)$$

Directly measuring stagnation pressure with Kiel probes has the advantage of being simple to manufacture, adapt, and implement, but the flow blockage induced by the probe itself and the survival time of the probe in the harsh environment is worth considering. Additionally, the probe is submerged in a fluctuating transonic and supersonic flow, which makes shock losses through any leading bow shocks difficult to estimate. Lastly, the probe represents a point measurement instead of mass-averaging, which poses challenges to accurately describe stagnation pressure. Most of

the current research on pressure gain comes from the thrust stand-based EAP method that provides an area-integrated measurement, although the influence of base drag measurement and the assumption of uniformly choked flow at the exit plane cause inevitable uncertainty [16]. This method also requires an increased calibration effort. Measuring static pressure with CTAP protects sensors from heat loads but also relies on time-averaging of the pressure signal. In addition, CTAP-based methods also need to make assumptions about the exit Mach number and are also only one or multiple points of measurement. Therefore, it remains a challenge to accurately determine RDE performance in terms of total pressure increase.

There are only few studies about direct comparison of the above methods. The present work therefore endeavors to compare and analyze data from all three approaches using the same combustor and operating conditions. To this end, a recently commissioned thrust stand and base drag measurement system at TU Berlin is employed. This allows a comprehensive investigation of the variation of total pressure with different RDC configurations, including equivalence ratio, outlet restriction, and mass flux. Lastly, this allows a validation and assessment of each of the three techniques and provides the PGC community with a broad dataset for pressure gain measurements.

II. Experimental Setup

As displayed in Figure 2a, TU Berlin's RDC employs a simple design that allows for an easy change of components. Air and hydrogen are used in this study and the mass flow rate can be changed from 0.2 kg/s to 0.55 kg/s. The air in an annular oxidizer plenum is injected radially inward into the combustion annulus through a slit of height g , which can vary from 1.0 to 3.2 mm, while hydrogen is injected through a central injector plate with hundreds of holes distributed circumferentially around the perimeter of the outer wall of the combustion annulus. The outlet restriction at the exit plane of the combustor can be changed from 0 to 50% of the channel area. Additional information for the combustor design and results is available in [5, 17, 18].

Figure 2b shows an L-shaped Kiel probe that is installed in the exit plane and slightly upstream of the exit throat. The angle of the Kiel probe head is parallel to the axial direction of the combustor. The central Pitot tube is connected to a Kulite XTEL-190LM sensor by an internal capillary of some 150 mm. The Kiel shroud is made of a chrome-cobalt alloy with a high melting point. After thousands of runs, the high enthalpy flow at the combustor exit did not cause significant signs of probe wear.

Fig. 2 Experimental setup: (a) TU Berlin's RDC [19], (b) Kiel probe at the combustor exit, (c) thrust stand.

A thrust stand was recently designed and commissioned and is shown in Figure 2c. The combustion chamber is mounted to a sled with one degree of freedom along the axial direction. The sled sits atop a solid fixed frame. The movable sled and the fixed frame are axially guided with linear bearings and a high-frequency S-form load cell (ME Systeme KD80s, ± 5 kN connected to an ME Systeme GSV-6K amplifier) fixes their positions. The axial thrust caused by the jet exiting the combustor transfers through the sled to the force sensor. To minimize the influence of the pressurized tubes on the thrust measurement, gas connections spanning the gap between the frame and sled are rigidly fixed perpendicular to the thrust axis. A great deal of attention must be given to the calibration of the load cell, as the connections represent a static resistance to the thrust. Attaching weights via winches to the sled to apply a force is simple and low in cost (see, e.g. Feleo et al. [16] or Kato et al. [20]). In the present study, a direct calibration force is applied in the form of a screw jack loading the aft end of the combustion chamber, as shown in 3a. A second pre-calibrated force

sensor (ME Systeme KM26, 0...5 kN coupled to an ME Systeme GSV-6K amplifier) is installed between the screw jack (Maedler NP/I) and the combustor to ensure a known calibration input force to the thrust stand. By turning the screw jack, a direct calibration up to 10 kN can be easily conducted. This method enables the compensation of influences that distort the KD80s measurement such as the fuel and air tubes or sled friction especially as the screwjack applies the force at the same location where the RDC thrust acts.

To avoid interfering vibrations induced by the detonation wave propagation and the natural frequency of the thrust stand, the measuring setup was installed with a spring (Gutekunst D-288Z-40) and damper (Wagner HP3) system as shown in Fig. 3b. This also allows a preloading of the force sensor and attenuates ringing of the step response, resulting in a shorter settling time.

Fig. 3 Examples of (a) screw jack and (b) springs and dampers used in the calibration system.

As shown in Figure 4, a base drag measurement system is designed which provides 7 ports on the outlet restriction plate of the center body for sensors installation at different radial positions. The sensor taps are distributed in a 'spiral' shape to reduce the influence of asymmetrical pressure distribution on the base drag measurement. A similar system is used on the outer flange, albeit with fewer pressure taps (3 taps) as the influence of that portion was shown to be significantly less [8]. Each port is connected to a pressure sensor with a steel capillary tube and a thin silicone tube. The capillary tubes for the ports in the center body are routed out through a conduit in the center of the center body due to design constraints of the RDC. The base drag pressure are measured by NXP MPX5050DP and MPX5010DP series piezoresistive differential pressure transducers. The ambient port of the differential pressure sensors were connected to a manifold and a diffusor to avoid the influence of any possible ambient pressure variation in the vicinity of the test stand caused by the exhaust of the RDC. It should be noted that the Kiel probe is not installed when thrust measurements are being conducted due to the natural blockage of Kiel probe itself to the exiting flow and its influence on the pressure field on the base of the RDC.

To also estimate the total pressure, a Kulite sensor in CTAP configuration is placed close to the combustor exit. The length of the capillary tube is around 1.3 m which will cause a significant attenuation of the fluctuation of the pressure signal. An average of the static pressure from it will be used in the Mach-corrected CTAP method. Detailed tests were conducted with Kiel probe and CTAP mounted in the RDC and thrust stand for varying air gaps ($A_{3,1}/A_{3,2} = 0.144, 0.230, 0.287$ and 0.460), outlet restrictions ($A_8/A_{3,2} = 1, 0.84, 0.75, 0.67$ and 0.50) and mass flux $J_8 = 50 \dots 600 \text{ kg/s/m}^2$

III. Results and Discussion

To get a better understanding of the availability of the aforementioned three total pressure measurement methods for different configurations, a detailed comparison is conducted in this study with varying mass flux, air gaps and outlet restrictions. First, time resolved pressure traces from the Kiel probe and CTAP are presented to show the stable section for pressure extraction. The pressure gain is then obtained by the comparison between static pressure in the air plenum (assuming low Mach number), and the total pressure at the combustor exit. The dependence of total pressure and pressure gain on the configuration will be further investigated. Additionally, based on the currently commissioned thrust stand, the net thrust and the base drag distributed on the outlet plate and the outer flange will be analysed for the

Fig. 4 Example of base drag measurements system, showing seven sensor ports on the centerbody and three ports on the outer flange.

Port No.	Radius (mm)	Area (mm ²)
1	10	339.29
2	14	351.86
3	18	452.39
4	22	552.92
5	26	653.45
6	30	753.98
7	34	1669.19
8	56.67	6639.28
9	72	6934.65
10	87.34	8417.72

Table 1 Distribution of base drag ports for $A_8/A_{3,2} = 0.75$.

EAP method. Lastly, a comparison of these three methods with different configurations will also be investigated. The purpose of current work is to verify the performance of these three methods on total pressure measurement and compare the advantages and limitations for each method.

A. Direct Kiel Probe Method and Mach-Corrected CTAP Method

Figure 5 shows two example time traces measured with the Kiel probe at the combustor exit plate and a Kulite sensor in the CTAP configuration mounted on the combustor chamber. The last 50 ms stable section was chosen. A moving average method with a 500-point window was applied to extract the the total pressure at the exit and the static pressure in the combustion chamber, respectively. As shown in the figure, the first blue section in each plot shows the cold reactants before the detonation. There is a following obvious pressure spike after ignition and then settling to a constant value after a period of time 50-75 ms. Viscous losses in the capillary occurs in both setups, which leads to a significant signal attenuation. The zoomed in views show the transients due to the passing oblique shock, which can be used in wave speed calculation. Because the CTAP can only transmit the static pressure, the averaged pressure of the CTAP is lower than that of the Kiel probe, as expected.

Fig. 5 Examples of (a) total pressure data acquired with a Kiel probe and (b) static pressure data acquired with a CTAP, $A_{3,1}/A_{3,2} = 0.144$, $A_8/A_{3,2} = 0.75$, $\dot{m} = 0.4$ kg/s, $\phi \approx 1$.

These techniques are applied for pressure data with varying RDC geometries. For clarity's sake, here only one air injector (1 mm air gap) and five different outlet restrictions over the range of J_8 as an example are compared. In Figure 6, the total pressure and pressure gain measured by the Kiel probe method and the Mach-corrected CTAP method are compared. Walters et al. [21] proposed using the exit throat area to oxidizer injection area $A_8/A_{3,1}$ to analyze the influence of the geometry on the RDC performance. In this study, a 0% outlet restriction combined with the 1 mm air gap corresponds to $A_8/A_{3,1} = 3.479$, likewise a 50% outlet restriction combined with the 1 mm air gap corresponds to $A_8/A_{3,1} = 1.7395$. It can be seen from Figure 6a and 6b that the total pressure measured by both methods follows the same trend and falls within the same band (1-7 bar(a)), indicating that the average stagnation pressure arrives at similar values for both approaches. There is an obvious drop of pressure gain in the low mass flux section ($< 200 \text{ kg/s/m}^2$), where the out flow is subsonic and transonic [5] (will be further analysed in Figure 13a). The pressure gain measured by Kiel probe is slightly higher than that from the Mach number CTAP method at the corresponding mass flux, which will be better shown in 13a. The exit flow's stagnation pressure and pressure gain significantly increase with increasing mass flux, and also with increasing outlet blockage, which are also visible in the previous results of Kiel probe measurements from [5, 6]. The best pressure gain across all geometries in the current study is -0.075.

Fig. 6 Results of (a) stagnation pressure and (c) pressure gain measured by direct Kiel probe method, as well as (b) stagnation pressure and (d) pressure gain measured by the Mach-corrected CTAP method for various $J_8 = 50 \dots 600 \text{ kg/s/m}^2$ and outlet restrictions ($A_8/A_{3,2} = 1 \dots 0.5$). All configurations were at an equivalence ratio of $\phi \approx 1$. Data for $A_{3,1}/A_{3,2} = 0.144$ is shown as an example.

It can be seen that the total pressure measured by Kiel method for 0% outlet restriction configuration shows the same trend with the data for other outlet restrictions, while there is obvious forks when it is calculated by CTAP method. As mentioned in the introduction, both EAP and Mach-corrected CTAP method have the assumption of sonic condition at the exit throat. The hollow markers in Figure 6b and 6d represent the cases where mach number assumption breaks

down due to the low mass flux, which are determined by the corresponding static pressure at the combustor exit that is lower than the atmospheric values, as shown in Figure 7a. This sub-atmospheric pressure is not reasonable for a subsonic flow. Therefore, a correction of the Mach number is a non-trivial task for both of the Mach number assumption based methods. The 0% outlet restriction violates the assumption the most, probably due to low mass flux and lack of a "throat" in this geometry, which is a necessary design for both CTAP and EAP methods.

Figure 7b compares the total pressure from the Kiel probe method and Mach-corrected CTAP method for different air gaps, outlet restrictions, and mass fluxes. The correlation coefficient is around 96.72% and the regression line is close to a 1-1 relationship, indicating that these two methods have a good agreement in total pressure measurement. Based on previous analysis, the total pressure can not be measured correctly by Mach-corrected CTAP method for 0% outlet restriction. Therefore, the 0% outlet restriction is excluded from consideration in this plot. The zoomed in view highlights the cases where the Mach number assumption breaks down.

Fig. 7 (a) Calculated static pressure in the combustor exit for the Mach-corrected CTAP method as a function of J_8 , and (b) $p_{t,4}$ from Mach-corrected CTAP method versus $p_{t,8}$ from Kiel probe method for all conditions evaluated without Mach number correction applied.

B. Equivalent Available Pressure (EAP)

Compared to the two aforementioned methods, measuring EAP needs the most instrumentation, which makes the application of this method more challenging although it requires no instrumentation within the hot gas path, which is a benefit for longer duration testing. The load cell, the influence of pressurized gas supply tubes, and the loss of non-axial forces etc. all need to be taken into consideration in order to obtain an accurate thrust measurement. In addition, there needs to be a bluff body nozzle for EAP, which induces the base drag behind the exit plate, accounting for nearly 12% of the gross thrust [7].

For the studied RDC, a thrust of up to 600 N is expected, depending on the configuration. Figure 8 shows the thrust data for an operating condition at 0.4 kg/s air mass flow. A significant increase of the produced thrust during burn time is observable, as is the typical step response of the frame to changes in the applied force after ignition. The raw data is re-sampled to match the actual data frequency of the employed amplifier and to filter out noisy outliers. An average thrust is obtained in the last section of the signal to avoid being biased by unevenly cutting through oscillations.

Figure 9a shows the base drag pressure measured over the courses of a single run by ten piezoresistive differential transducers which are distributed radially on the outlet plate and the outer flange. The gauge pressure from seven sensors on the aft-facing centerbody plate drops dramatically after ignition while showing less pressure drop for the remaining three sensor on the flange. This is in concurrence with the common understanding that total base drag pressure mainly depends on the low pressure behind the exit plate.

By averaging the tail of the base drag traces in Figure 9a for each sensor, the base drag distribution on the outlet plate and flange can be obtained. This variation of base drag pressure and corresponding forces for varying mass flux is given in Figure 9b and 9c, where each color corresponds to one mass flux configuration. It can be seen that there are

Fig. 8 Example thrust measurements, showing time trace of S-type load cell for $\dot{m} = 0.4$ kg/s, which was tested for 400 ms with $A_8/A_{3,2} = 0.84$ and at an equivalence ratio of $\phi \approx 1$. A selection of important features is highlighted.

approximately two distinguishing base drag profiles for the different mass fluxes. For a low mass flux (< 208.7 kg/s/m²), where the operating mode of the RDC experienced a single wave to multi wave transition, the base drag shows a 'V-like' shape where a local minimum in pressure occurs around the sensor in position five. However, when mass flux reach above 208.7 kg/s/m², where the stable single wave mode was observed, sensor 1 at the innermost position shows the lowest pressure. Previous results from Fievisohn et al. [15] and Brophy et al. [13] showed different base drag pressure profile shapes, which could be caused by many possible factors, including a conduit sticking out of the middle of the centerbody of TU Berlin's RDC, which will affect the way the pressure can communicated across the face of the centerbody and could very reasonably change the profiles, and also the operating modes of the RDC, the numbers and locations of base drag sensors. Another possibility is that for the low mass flux cases the exhaust does not really converge again and allows air from infinity to flow into the center of the outlet plate. For this particular configuration this effect might be exacerbated by the aforementioned conduit for the capillaries of the base drag sensors sticking out of the outlet plate. The pressure profile is different from the base force profile in that the 'v-like' shape, even though apparent, is mitigated by the increasing area. The base force profile is much closer to an exponential function for mass fluxes larger than 126.2 kg/s/m² where the 'v-like' shape of the pressure profile causes a local flattening of the curve. While the pressure difference on outer flange is lower than that on the centerbody, the larger area on the outer flange means that the net base drag force on the flange should not be neglected, as shown in Figure 9c.

Fig. 9 (a) Example of the low-pass filtered base drag time traces of ten sensors for $A_8/A_{3,2} = 0.84$, $A_{3,1}/A_{3,2} = 0.144$, $\dot{m} = 0.4$ kg/s, $\phi \approx 1$. (b) Pressure and (c) force distribution on the centerbody and the outer flange for $A_8/A_{3,2} = 0.84$, $A_{3,1}/A_{3,2} = 0.144$, $J_{3,2} = 50 \dots 282$ kg/s/m², $\phi \approx 1$.

The net thrust measured from the load cell, the total base drag at the aft end and the gross thrust for varying mass

flux are illustrated in Figure 10. The net thrust increases with the increasing mass flux dramatically while the base drag grows more slowly, accounting for between 12.78% and 56.98% of the gross thrust in the studied mass flux range. It is apparent that the proportion of the base drag force contributing to the net thrust diminishes with higher mass fluxes. It is notable that for very low mass fluxes ($J_8 = 50 \text{ kg/s/m}^2$ and $J_8 = 75 \text{ kg/s/m}^2$) the fraction even becomes as large as 56.98% of the gross thrust. This result might be artificially high due to a relatively high sensor noise in the base drag sensors and a low thrust at these mass fluxes. The expected general trend that with higher mass fluxes the impact of the base drag becomes smaller can clearly be observed. The highest gross thrust for 1 mm air gap and 16% outlet restriction stays at 551 N.

Fig. 10 Variation of base drag, net thrust and gross thrust as a function of J_8 . These cases are for $A_{3,1}/A_{3,2} = 0.144$, $A_8/A_{3,2} = 0.5$ and $\phi \approx 1$.

Based on the measured gross thrust, Eq. 2 and Eq. 3, the total pressure can be computed and is shown in Figure 11a. Compared with the two aforementioned methods, EAP method measured a lower total pressure with the maximum of 5.8 bar. The pressure gain in Figure 11b shows a linear increasing trend, which is different to the other two methods, but falls into the same range of -0.2...-0.7. The hollow markers in Figure 11b represent the cases where the Mach number assumption does not hold. The static pressure at the exit throat is derived from Eq. 2 and given in Figure 11c. It can be seen that for the EAP method more cases seem to fail the choked outlet criteria.

Fig. 11 Results of (a) total pressure, (b) pressure gain (c) and calculated static pressure at the combustor exit for EAP method for $J_8 = 50 \dots 600 \text{ kg/s/m}^2$ and $A_8/A_{3,2} = 1 \dots 0.5$. All configurations were at an equivalence ratio of $\phi \approx 1$. Data from $A_{3,1}/A_{3,2} = 0.144$ is taken as an example.

C. Low Mach Number Correction

As shown in Figure 7a and Figure 11c, the calculated static pressure by Mach-corrected CTAP and EAP method at the exit throat is lower than the atmospheric values for some low mass flux cases which would mean that the flow is not choked [22]. To correct the Mach number from the CTAP method, the area-Mach relations in the isentropic flow is utilized and assume $p_8 = p_0$, as shown in Eq. 6 and Eq. 7. Mach number for EAP method can be corrected by Eq. 5 with the same assumption of $p_8 = p_0$.

A comparison of the original total pressure measured directly from CTAP method and EAP method, and the corrected total pressure with low Mach number correction applied is shown in Figure 12. It can be seen that the corrected

pressure of CTAP is consistently lower than the original pressure, which means the CTAP method will overestimate the total pressure if the low Mach number correction is not considered, while the corrected pressure of EAP is higher than the original data, indicating that the EAP method will underestimate the total pressure without low Mach number correction. This trend was also found in previous results [15].

Fig. 12 Original and corrected total pressure derived from (a) Mach-corrected CTAP method and (b) EAP method, $A_{3,1}/A_{3,2} = 0.144$, $\phi \approx 1$.

D. Comparison of Total Pressure Measurement Methods

All three methods have their own limitations, so it is therefore of interest to further determine whether the method applied in this study produces similar results. Figure 13a reproduces Figure 7b but with low Mach number correction. It can be seen from the figure that correlation coefficient is 99.05%, which is higher than that of Figure 7b due to the good agreement at the low mass flux zone. Again data is not consistently above or below the 1-1 reference line, which might be caused by the quality of the time averaging result for CTAP method in a extremely unsteady environment, but also raises the question that the reliability of each method in a specific Mach number condition. Based on the low Mach number correction results and the sonic assumption at the exit throat, it can be seen that the majority of the outflow in Figure 13a agrees the Mach number assumption, but the few transonic outflow will lead to a smaller total pressure than the actual pressure for the Kiel method due to the detached bow shock ahead of the probe [4].

Fig. 13 Comparison of (a) Mach-corrected CTAP method vs. direct Kiel method, and (b) EAP method vs. direct Kiel method and (c) Mach-corrected CTAP method vs. EAP method for all conditions evaluated with Mach number correction applied.

To further compare the Mach number assumption based method and direct Kiel method, total pressure data from

EAP vs. Kiel is plotted in Figure 13b. Note that Kiel probe will block a part of the out flow so it could not be installed to simultaneously measure the two techniques from a single test run. Therefore, aligning the data from these two methods is challenging. Experience has shown relatively good repeatability in the test rig, an comparison could be achieved by comparing the same configurations and same mass fluxes between separately taken data. Figure 13b compares the regression results between EAP and Kiel method with low Mach number correction. Although there is more scatter in the data due to required separated test, the correlation coefficient between both methods is surprisingly good and higher than 90%. Even though the error is not as small as it is between Kiel probes and CTAP, a trend between Kiel probes and EAP can be seen. For medium pressures (around 1.5 bar to 3.5 bar) EAP seems to underestimate compared to the Kiel probes. After that the underestimation seems to become less significant. In addition to the run-to-run repeatability, a number of other mechanisms may also contribute to the scatter. Since the base drag has a big influence on the gross thrust of the EAP, any errors and especially sensor noise in the base drag measurements may cause a large error in the EAP computation, especially for low mass flux cases where the base drag is small. Figure 13c shows the total pressure measured by EAP method versus that of the Mach-corrected CTAP method. Although the scatter is still there, the agreement between these two methods is good with around 89% of the correlation coefficient. The correlation shows that the CTAP starts of overestimating relative to the EAP but ends up agreeing well for the higher end of the recorded mass fluxes while still having a fairly large scattering. In short, the difference among the techniques utilized in this study is quite small, and this conclusion could be further validated by reducing the uncertainties of these methods in the following research.

IV. Conclusions

In this study, the comparability of several methods for determining the total pressure in an RDC was studied. A newly commissioned thrust stand was used to collect data for a broad range of operating and boundary conditions encompassing changes in the air injector stiffness, the reactant mass flux, and the outlet nozzle shape and contraction ratio. A CTAP was placed close to the outlet to also estimate total pressure. Both newly implemented techniques were then compared against the previous Kiel probe experiments, providing an assessment of their applicability, advantages and drawbacks. On a practical level, this extends the PGC community's tool chest with respect to RDC performance quantification. Scientifically, the comparison is a step towards an enhanced understanding of the interaction of these diagnostics with the highly transient and high-enthalpy exhaust flow, as well as of the nature of stagnation pressure gain in RDCs itself which will be deepened by future research.

(1) The Kiel probe method offers a direct measurement of the total pressure, which produces 1 to 7 bar(a) for the investigated mass flux, inlet and outlet geometries. The total pressure rises linear with the mass flux. However, for transonic/supersonic outflow, measured values may be underestimated due to the detached bow shock at the Kiel head. This however supports Kiel probe measured pressures as being generally conservative.

(2) The Mach-corrected CTAP method (sometimes referred to as the NPS method) also has the capability to measure total pressure with reduced instrumentation. In the case presented it only needed one sensor instead of eleven sensors plus a calibration load cell for the EAP method. It is however limited by the outlet plate geometry and the mass flux. A Mach number correction could further expand the applicability, but an actual outlet throat is still generally needed. Compared to the Kiel probe the CTAP shows an offset of +0.07 bar minus 3.7% of the pressure with a mean square error of 0.99.

(3) Accurate gross thrust measurements depend on a well-calibrated load cell and the base drag measurement system. By changing the configuration of the RDC, up to 600 N of net thrust were measured. The base drag distribution on the outlet plate shows a shifting local low pressure zone with varying mass flux and accounts for between 12.78% and 56.98% of the gross thrust. The EAP method produced almost the same range of total pressure and pressure gain compared with CTAP and Kiel methods. The EAP, compared to the Kiel probe shows a an offset of -0.17 bar minus 5% of the pressure with a mean square error of 0.91.

(4) The CTAP method will overestimate the total pressure without a low mach number correction while the EAP method shows an opposite trend. Additionally, the corrected low Mach number at the exit throat for the low mass flux range falls into a 0 to 1 band, which divides the speed of the outflow of the RDC for the low mass flux into two zones (subsonic and transonic). This could be helpful to further explain the difference between Kiel and CTAP on the total pressure measurements, considering the speed of the outflow can definitely influence the accuracy of the total pressure measurement results, especially for the Kiel probe.

(5) The comparison among EAP and the other two methods showed a large relative scattering which is expected due to the separated test. Stagnation pressure gain measured with a Kiel probe is in excellent agreement with CTAP data,

this holds true also for the EAP data despite the large number of calibrations that still have to be further considered. That means that Kiel probes and Mach-corrected CTAP can present EAP-like total pressure but with simpler implementation.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956803. The authors appreciate the help of Florian Ditsche for assistance with the thrust stand design and component selection.

References

- [1] Stefanizzi, M., Capurso, T., Filomeno, G., Torresi, M., and Pascasio, G., "Recent Combustion Strategies in Gas Turbines for Propulsion and Power Generation toward a Zero-Emissions Future: Fuels, Burners, and Combustion Techniques," *Energies*, Vol. 14, No. 20, 2021, p. 6694.
- [2] Ma, J. Z., Luan, M.-Y., Xia, Z.-J., Wang, J.-P., Zhang, S.-J., Yao, S.-B., and Wang, B., "Recent Progress, Development Trends, and Consideration of Continuous Detonation Engines," *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 58, No. 12, 2020, pp. 4976–5035.
- [3] Paxson, D. E., "Defining and Measuring Pressure Gain," *International Constant Volume and Detonation Combustion Workshop*, August 2019.
- [4] Bach, E., Thethy, B. S., Edgington-Mitchell, D., Rezay Haghdoost, M., Oliver Paschereit, C., Stathopoulos, P., and Bohon, M. D., "Kiel Probes for Stagnation Pressure Measurement in Rotating Detonation Combustors," *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 60, No. 6, 2022, pp. 3724–3735.
- [5] Bach, E., Stathopoulos, P., Paschereit, C. O., and Bohon, M. D., "Performance Analysis of a Rotating Detonation Combustor Based on Stagnation Pressure Measurements," *Combustion and Flame*, Vol. 217, 2020, pp. 21–36.
- [6] Bach, E., Paschereit, C., Stathopoulos, P., and Bohon, M. D., "An Empirical Model for Stagnation Pressure Gain in Rotating Detonation Combustors," *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute*, Vol. 38, No. 3, 2021, pp. 3807–3814.
- [7] Kaemming, T. A., and Paxson, D. E., "Determining the Pressure Gain of Pressure Gain Combustion, AIAA Paper 2018-4567," July 2018.
- [8] Fievisohn, R. T., Hoke, J. L., and Holley, A. T., "Equivalent Available Pressure Measurements on a Laboratory RDE, AIAA Paper 2020-2285," January 2020.
- [9] Harroun, A. J., Heister, S. D., and Ruf, J. H., "Computational and Experimental Study of Nozzle Performance for Rotating Detonation Rocket Engines," *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, Vol. 37, No. 5, 2021, pp. 660–673.
- [10] Codoni, J. R., Birindelli, G., Thoeny, A., and Brophy, C. M., "Experimental Approaches for Obtaining a Temporally- and Spatially-Averaged Representative Static Pressure for Rotating Detonation Engines, AIAA Paper 2022-2369," January 2022.
- [11] Paxson, D. E., and Hoke, J. L., "Time Averaged Pressure Measurement in Fundamentally Unsteady Pressure Gain Combustion Systems," *JANNAF 45th Combustion Subcommittee Meeting*, 2012.
- [12] Brophy, C. M., Codoni, J. R., and Ten Eyck, J. A., "Interpretation of Capillary Tube Average Pressure Measurements in RDEs, AIAA Paper 2019-1744," January 2019.
- [13] Brophy, C. M., and Codoni, J. R., "Experimental Performance Characterization of an RDE Using Equivalent Available Pressure, AIAA Paper 2019-4212," August 2019.
- [14] Klopsch, R., Garan, N., Bohon, M., Bach, E., Asli, M., and Stathopoulos, P., "2D Euler Modeling of Rotating Detonation Combustion in Preparation for Turbomachinery Matching, AIAA Paper 2022-0836," January 2022.
- [15] Fievisohn, R. T., Hoke, J., and Holley, A. T., "Experimental Measurements of Equivalent Available Pressure-Lessons Learned, AIAA Paper 2022-0833," January 2022.
- [16] Feleo, A., Chacon, F., and Gamba, M., "Uncertainties in Thrust and EAP Measurements of a Rotating Detonation Combustor with Axial Air Inlet, AIAA Paper 2020-3856," August 2020.
- [17] Bluemner, R., Bohon, M. D., Paschereit, C. O., and Gutmark, E. J., "Counter-rotating wave mode transition dynamics in an RDC," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, Vol. 44, No. 14, 2019, pp. 7628–7641.

- [18] Bluemner, R., Bohon, M. D., Paschereit, C. O., and Gutmark, E. J., "Effect of inlet and outlet boundary conditions on rotating detonation combustion," *Combustion and Flame*, Vol. 216, 2020, pp. 300–315.
- [19] Bach, E., Paschereit, C. O., Stathopoulos, P., and Bohon, M. D., "RDC Operation and Performance with Varying Air Injector Pressure Loss, AIAA Paper 2020-0199," January 2020.
- [20] Kato, Y., Ishihara, K., Gawahara, K., Matsuoka, K., Kasahara, J., Matsuo, A., and Funaki, I., "Thrust Measurement of Rotating Detonation Engine by Sled Test, AIAA Paper 2014-4034," July 2014.
- [21] Walters, I. V., Journell, C. L., Lemcherfi, A. I., Gejji, R. M., Heister, S. D., and Slabaugh, C. D., "Performance Characterization of a Natural Gas-Air Rotating Detonation Engine at Elevated Pressure, AIAA Paper 2019-4214," August 2019.
- [22] Liepmann, H. W., and Roshko, A., *Elements of Gas Dynamics*, Dover Publications, Inc., 2001.